

Ion-Solvent Interaction from Apparent Molar Volume of Sr(NO₃)₂ and Cd(NO₃)₂ in Aquo-organic Solvents at different Temperatures

D. K. DAS

Department of Chemistry, S. C. S. College, Puri and

P. B. DAS*

State Forensic Science Laboratory, Rasulgarh, Bhubaneswar-751 010

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WATER at ordinary temperature has a quasicrystalline structure. A dynamic equilibrium seems to exist between the three-dimensional hydrogen bonded clusters and the denser monomers¹, (H₂O)₆ ⇌ (H₂O)₄. Electrolytes which dissolve in water has been classified as structure-makers or structure-breakers depending on whether the above equilibrium shifts to the left or right. Frank and Wen¹ gave a picture in which an ion is surrounded by concentric regions of water molecules, polarised, immobilised and electrostricted by the ion, analogous to a kind of freezing, which they called the region-A. The molecules in the region-C has the normal three-dimensional network as stated above. The centrosymmetric structures imposed by the ion in the region-A is incompatible with the normal structure in the region-C and there is a tendency to resist such order and balance between the two competing forces gives rise to a region-B. Ions with a low charge density has a smaller width of region-A and larger width of region-B are net structure-breakers. On the other hand, ions with a high charge density show an opposite behaviour and are net structure-makers.

The organic solvents dioxane, glycol and methanol are miscible with water at all solvent

compositions, and their dielectric constant and dipole moments are very much different. Water is both an electron donor and acceptor. Hence studies of their aqueous mixtures become an interesting field to explore, particularly of the ionic processes accompanying the solution of the strong electrolytes. It becomes relevant to enquire whether a given mixed solvent resists the centrosymmetric ordering of the ion more or less than of pure water. From this point of view, the apparent molar volume of solutions of Sr(NO₃)₂ and Cd(NO₃)₂ at 10, 20 and 30 wt. % of dioxane+water and glycol+water have been measured at C ≤ 0.1 mol dm⁻³ at 30-45° and 30-40° for methanol+water mixtures.

Experimental

All the salts were of 'extra pure' (E. Merck) grade. The preparation of the solvents and solutions were the same as that described before¹. The density of the solutions and solvents was determined by pycnometers with buoyancy correction and is the same as described before¹. All sorts of precautions were taken to check evaporation. Density readings were precise upto 0.0002 g cm⁻³. The concentration range was 0.1-0.001 mol dm⁻³.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) calculated from the equation,

$$\phi = \frac{M}{\rho_0} - \left(\frac{\rho - \rho_0}{\rho_0} \right) \frac{10^3}{C}$$

ϕ was found to vary linearly with C^{1/2}, i.e. fit in the empirical Masson's equation²,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^\circ + S_v C^{1/2}$$

where, ϕ^o is the apparent molar volume and S_v, the limiting slope. The values of ϕ^o and S_v obtained from the plots are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF ϕ^o (cm³ mol⁻¹) AND S_v (cm^{3/2} mol^{-1/2})

Temp. °C	Sr(NO ₃) ₂						Cd(NO ₃) ₂					
	10%		20%		30%		10%		20%		30%	
	ϕ ^o	S _v	ϕ ^o	S _v	ϕ ^o	S _v	ϕ ^o	S _v	ϕ ^o	S _v	ϕ ^o	S _v
Dioxane+Water												
30	36.32	30.06	37.44	27.78	38.92	26.01	41.45	27.72	43.45	27.69	44.80	26.89
35	37.21	25.98	39.31	24.72	42.42	25.92	42.83	26.58	44.95	26.53	47.88	26.66
40	38.43	24.68	40.82	25.28	43.75	23.20	43.52	27.12	45.45	27.47	48.97	24.30
45	40.23	24.97	42.45	24.30	46.73	23.80	44.62	26.93	47.47	28.42	50.23	28.77
Methanol+Water												
30	35.23	25.44	36.23	27.22	37.43	27.34	38.50	29.20	40.25	28.18	42.21	29.43
35	36.10	25.63	37.55	28.54	37.42	23.22	39.61	25.60	41.32	27.53	43.24	26.04
40	37.21	26.90	39.23	27.75	41.22	22.24	40.73	24.61	43.45	24.01	45.73	28.22
45	39.14	27.20	40.81	28.30	43.44	22.50	41.61	24.45	45.48	27.22	48.34	28.45
Glycol+Water												
30	33.62	25.38	34.65	26.01	35.82	24.62	36.21	26.27	37.25	29.30	39.12	28.18
35	34.75	26.19	35.43	27.88	36.62	27.78	37.34	28.44	38.72	27.91	40.80	28.20
40	35.75	28.70	37.44	26.42	39.08	28.20	33.52	26.58	39.92	26.52	42.22	26.42

Dependence of ϕ° on temperature : It is evident from Table 1 that ϕ° increases with the increase in temperature for both $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in aquo-organic solvents. This increase can be explained on the basis of primary and secondary solvation layers which appear to be formed around an ion⁸. At higher temperature the solvent from the secondary solvent layers is released to the bulk resulting in the expansion of the solution rapidly than that of the pure solvent⁴.

Limiting slope (S_v) :

At all the temperatures, the limiting apparent slope (S_v) of the Masson's equation (Table 1) is positive, suggesting ion-ion interaction. This may be attributed due to the change in mobility of the ions due to the change in the dielectric constant. Moreover, the plot of S_v vs wt. % of organic solvent is linear and the slope is of the order, $(G+W) > (M+W) > (D+W)$, indicating the structure-promoting order.

Dependence of ϕ° on organic solvents : The increase in ϕ° with the increase in organic solvent (Table 1) may be attributed due to low surface charge density, as a result of which the electrostatic attraction is more in a medium of low dielectric constant. Hence, ion-solvent interaction would also be more and consequently ϕ° will be larger and the order is $(D+W) > (M+W) > (G+W)$. Further, the plot of ϕ vs $1/\epsilon$, the reciprocal of the dielectric constant, is found to be linear for all the cases and the slope values of these plots follow the order, $(M+W) > (D+W) > (G+W)$ indicating the dependence of the dielectric constant of the medium, which is in agreement with the observations of Gopal *et al.*^{5,6}. This can be explained as follows. Dioxane, because of its bulky size, is not accommodated in the solvent structure and hence it causes a breakdown in the three-dimensional water structure. Amongst glycol and methanol, glycol has the tendency to break the hydrogen bond more readily than methanol, but from ϕ° values, the reverse is found to be true. This is probably due to the low ion-solvent interaction which is unable to break the hydrogen bond. So the ion-solvent interaction in the present study follow the order, $(\text{dioxane} + \text{water}) > (\text{methanol} + \text{water}) > (\text{glycol} + \text{water})$. A similar conclusion has also been drawn from the conductivity data⁷.

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Studies on the Physicochemical Properties of Cyclohexane/Ethylene Glycol Emulsions Stabilised by different Surfactants

I. P. PANDEY

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. (P. G.) College, Dehra Dun-248 001

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THE properties and characteristics of oil/water and water/oil emulsions have been studied¹⁻⁷ extensively. However, survey of literature reveals that oil/oil emulsions have been investigated to a very limited extent⁸. Hence it was thought worthwhile to prepare cyclohexane/ethylene glycol emulsions and study their properties.

Experimental

Cyclohexane, ethylene glycol (B.D.H.) and cetyl alcohol, Ambupon Pdr. and Super-N-Dedenol (HICO, India) were used. Oil/oil emulsions were prepared as follows. A 0.5% solutions of the emulsifiers, viz. Ambupon Pdr, Super-N-Dedenol and cetyl alcohol were prepared in cyclohexane. To a fixed amount of the solution, ethylene glycol in varying proportions was added to obtain cyclohexane/ethylene glycol ratios 1:9, 1:8, 1:7, 1:6, 1:5, 1:4, 1:3, 1:2 and 1:1. Various amounts of water, i.e. 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 ml were added to the emulsion (1:1). The emulsions were then prepared by mixing them for ~2 min in a Redimix mixer. Surface tension, viscosity and conductance of the emulsions were then measured by drop-weight method, Ostwald's viscometer and conductivity bridge (W. T. W., German make), respectively. The temperature was maintained at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that with the increase in the amount of ethylene glycol, the emulsions become more viscous and stable. The observation also reveals that higher the amount of ethylene glycol more is the viscosity of emulsions which favours the stability by reducing the mobility of the droplets and preventing the coalescence.

The study of surface tension reveals that as the quantity of ethylene glycol increases, the surface tension decreases. It has been reported⁹ that higher viscosity and lower surface tension favour the emulsification and emulsion stability. Hence it is suggested that the emulsion having lower surface tension and higher viscosity is the most stable one. The enhancement of stability with the increase of ethylene glycol ratio suggests the role of OH group and hydrogen-bonding in stabilising the emulsion. Further, Table 1 shows that the lowering of surface tension and increase of viscosity is maximum for all